
STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE YOUR ACTIVE LISTENING SKILLS

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Abstract: One of the most critical skills in effective communication is active listening. Using active listening techniques can help you build and maintain relationships, solve problems, improve processes and retain information. In this article, we discuss active listening techniques that will help improve your active listening skills.

Keywords: Non-verbal, verbal characteristics, optimistic words, empathy, active listening techniques.

Active listening is a soft skill that requires you to focus on a speaker completely, understand their message, reflect on what's being said, respond thoughtfully and retain the information for later. Verbal and non-verbal active listening techniques help you focus and show that you're engaged. Active listening basically means the ability/habit to listen to the speaker with full concentration using all of your senses. Active Listening is an integral part of interpersonal skills which can be developed with disciplined practice, as it is not something that we are born with. Patience is the key to the successful progression towards mastering active listening.¹

¹ <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/active-listening-skills>

Non-Verbal Characteristics of Active Listener

Maintaining eye contact and appropriate physical posture are important traits an active listener demonstrates.

1. Maintaining Eye Contact

An active listener ensures that they have developed and maintained eye contact with the speaker. In addition to eye contact active listener seldom sets themselves apart with smiles or facial expression that is appropriate to the given situation.

2. Physical Posture

The second most important non-verbal sign of an active listener is physical posture. During interpersonal conversations, most of the time an active listener will lean forward to some extent. This not only displays interest but is also involved in the conversation.

3. Hand Movements

Over and above that, hand movements and gestures play a pivotal role in non-verbal active listening. It is said that an active listener talks not only with words but their actions speak louder.

4. Avoids Distractions

In this world of technology, it has become very easy to distract listeners. All you need to hear is a notification bell on your cell phone. You will notice that an active listener is not too concerned about a phone call or a phone notification. Active listeners are seldom ignorant of external stimuli making them engaged and focus better.

Verbal Characteristics of an Active Listener

Apart from non-verbal features, let's look at some verbal features an active listener displays.

1. Remembering

An active listener most of the time remembers key pointers or key information shared by the speaker.

2. Encourages Question and Answer

Not only question and answer is a trait an active listener displays but also it acts as feedback to the speaker. A speaker who did not get too many questions is either too perfect or not at all up to the mark. An active listener will without fail question the speaker about something from the topic discussed. The speaker can, on the other hand, also question you about what he or she is talking about to check to see whether you are actively listening to them or not.

3. Usage of Optimistic Words

An active listener often will reinforce the speaker with words like “yes”, “absolutely correct”, and “your right”. This not only boosts the confidence of the speaker but also increases audience and speaker bonding.

4. Immediate Clarify

In case of a doubt or misunderstanding, an active listener won't just be on it. The need for immediate answers gets them to clarify confusion on the spot. They won't fear raising their hands from a crowd of 100 people to get their answers.

5. Open to Sharing Experiences

Post any speaker is done, they ask for feedback through conversations. An active listener will not hesitate to add value to the speaker's topic by narrating his/her own experience related to the discussed topic. ²

Some people are better at active listening than others. And some people have to use active listening more in their day-to-day lives than others. Teachers, therapists and barbers need to be able to engage with and really hear other people all day, every day, as part of their jobs. But everybody needs these skills. Whether you're

² <https://shcvaliaintschool.in/verbal-nonverbal-features-active-listeners/>

navigating work, family, romantic or other personal relationships, being good at actively listening to others has many benefits:

Improves empathy. Some people assume empathy — the ability to understand or feel compassion for someone — is innate, that you either have it or you don't. But over time, we've come to understand that — while not all people have the same capacity to empathize — it's more like a muscle. If you don't use it, it can atrophy. And if you overuse it, you can get empathy fatigue. Active listening requires you to practice empathy.

Whether your goal is providing great customer service or maintaining a close relationship with your teenager, putting yourself in somebody else's shoes is crucial. And there's a bonus: Being empathetic also helps us to practice self-compassion when we fall short.

Builds mutual trust. Duke explains that active listening allows us to establish trust, even in situations involving power imbalances. "For example," she says, "if an employee really feels that — despite the hierarchy — they're being heard and understood by their boss, that what they're saying really matters, it's going to breed trust and respect in that relationship." We all need to trust the people around us to lead, to follow and to take risks.

Demonstrates respect. There's a reason it's all Aretha Franklin asked for. When people respect each other, they have more self-confidence, healthier boundaries, greater commitment and ... well, they're just happier! When you demonstrate a genuine interest in what another person thinks and feels, you're communicating that you value them and, in turn, the other person feels validated. That counts for a lot, especially when a relationship, of any kind, is being tested.

Diffuse conflict. None of us want conflict, but it's an inevitable part of most meaningful relationships. According to Duke, active listening is crucial in those moments because it requires being open to what other people are saying. "When you need to have those hard, difficult conversations, actively listening will enable you to diffuse that conflict and get to that win-win a lot sooner," she reassures.

7 active listening techniques

We've compiled some tips for being a better listener. Remember though: It's important not to treat these different actions as a checklist. If you're focused on crossing off each item on this list, you're not focused on the discussion you're having at that moment! Instead, make a point of practicing these skills now with people you know and trust, so they feel more natural when the time comes for deeper engagements.

1. Set an intention: "I like to set an intention for any conversation," Duke says. What kind of intention you set depends on the kind of conversation you're having. Keep in mind, an intention is open-ended — where the conversation goes will depend on what the other person says. Instead of saying, "I want to prove that I'm right," for example, you might say, "I want to better understand why my colleague disagrees with me."

2. Mindful presence: It may seem obvious that you need to "be present" in a conversation, but it's often easier said than done. So, how can you make sure your mind and body are in the same place — and focused on the right thing? "I think the very first thing that I would do is get rid of your phone and other distractions," Duke advises. "Even if you're listening, having your phone in front of you communicates to the other person that what they're saying is not important to you. So, make sure that you're setting yourself up for successful active listening and that the person really has your full attention."

As Duke puts it, "Mindful presence involves coming back to the moment, time and time again. Because our minds will wander. We're human."

3. Ask questions

One way to stay firmly in the moment is to ask questions. Those questions may involve reflecting back what somebody said to ensure you're understanding them correctly, asking them to elaborate on a point they made or inquiring as to how they feel about what they're saying.

“When we’re asking questions,” Duke says, “We’re really communicating to the other person that we’re understanding enough to ask insightful questions. In demonstrating our understanding, we might even bring up feelings or thoughts for them that they didn’t know they had. So, you’re creating a deeper rapport.”

4. Don’t focus on your response. Many people struggle to stay in the moment because they’re too busy thinking about the next thing they’re going to say. “Part of active listening is ridding yourself of that pressure — the pressure of needing to come up with some brilliant response,” Duke says. “If you’re thinking about your response, you can’t be listening.”

Most people will find this particular component of active listening difficult to do, as thinking about responding instead of listening is at least partially about anxiety. But if you can silence that inner voice, it will communicate volumes to the person you’re interacting with. “Not having a prepared response shows that you’re a learner, that you’re vulnerable, that you may not know the answer and that you’re also willing to learn,” Duke explains.³

5. Be nonjudgmental. In order to be truly willing to learn, you need to be open to hearing other people’s perspectives. That’s not easy, especially if you’re talking about difficult topics — and even more so if there’s a power imbalance between you and your conversation partner. Just like all of our minds wander from time to time, we all pass judgment. The key to being a good listener is recognizing it when it’s happening and purposefully adjusting your attitude. For example, if what you’re hearing is making you feel defensive or upset, you may need to step away from the conversation or reset your intention — in your mind or out loud. Remember that in active listening, the goal of the conversation is to understand, not to “win.”

6. Your posture tells a story: “Having a welcoming posture and body language shows that you’re open to receiving what the other person is saying and that you are taking a nonjudgmental, noncritical stance,” Duke explains.

³ <https://health.clevelandclinic.org/active-listening>

Developing active listening skills can help you accomplish the following:

Build connections: Active listening helps others feel comfortable sharing information with you. When you demonstrate your ability to sincerely listen to what others say, people will be more interested in communicating with you regularly. This can open opportunities to collaborate, get work done quickly or start new projects.

Develop trust: When people know they can speak freely to you without judgment or interruptions, they'll be more likely to confide in you. This is especially helpful when meeting a new customer or business contact with whom you want to develop a long-term working relationship.

Identify and solve problems: Developing your active listening skills will help you detect challenges others face or problems within projects. The quicker you can spot these issues, the sooner you can find a solution or create a plan to address them.

Increase your understanding of various topics: Great employees constantly strive to learn something new and grow their knowledge base. Because active listening helps you retain information, it also helps you better understand new topics and remember what you've learned so you can apply it in the future.

Avoid missing critical information: Practicing active listening means you're highly engaged with the speaker and can recall specific details. This is especially important when the speaker is providing instructions, training you on a new process or delivering a message you're responsible for passing along to others.⁴

Conclusion: Active listening is a critical soft skill that involves:

- Full Attention: Focusing entirely on the speaker without distractions.
- Comprehension: Understanding the speaker's message and intent.
- Reflection: Thinking about what is said and its implications.
- Thoughtful Response: Replying in a way that shows consideration of the speaker's words.

⁴ <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/active-listening-skills>

- Retention: Remembering key points for future discussions. Incorporating both verbal techniques, like asking questions or providing affirmations, and non-verbal techniques, such as maintaining eye contact or using encouraging body language, enhances engagement and communication effectiveness. This skill fosters better relationships and understanding in conversations.

References:

1. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/active-listening-skills>
2. <https://shcvaliainschool.in/verbal-nonverbal-features-active-listeners/>
3. <https://health.clevelandclinic.org/active-listening>
4. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/active-listening-skills>